

GENDER MAINSTREAMING LANDSCAPE OF DepEd DISTRICT OF SAN MATEO, ISABELA

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the current level of gender mainstreaming in the DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela, focusing on policy, people, enabling mechanisms, and programs, activities, and projects (PAPs). Using a descriptive-evaluative research design, the research employed both quantitative and qualitative methods, gathering data through surveys and structured interviews with stakeholders. The Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF) provided a basis for quantifying gender integration across identified dimensions. Descriptive statistics summarized the GMEF scores, while thematic analysis of interview data enriched quantitative findings with insights into the experiences and challenges faced by stakeholders. Results revealed that while foundational structures for gender mainstreaming exist, areas like policy enhancement and increased GAD (Gender and Development) expertise are needed for deeper institutional integration. The study concluded with recommendations to strengthen gender mainstreaming efforts, with the aim to create a more inclusive and equitable educational environment that aligns with national and international gender equality goals.

Keywords: *Gender mainstreaming, gender analysis, GAD Audit, Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF)*

INTRODUCTION

Gender equality in education is a crucial component of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 5, which aims to eliminate gender

disparities in all spheres of life, including education and employment. Despite progress, persistent gender gaps remain in labor market participation, leadership positions, and earnings, exacerbated by socio-cultural norms, economic barriers, and infrastructural deficiencies. For instance, in regions like the EU and Ghana, issues such as inadequate sanitation facilities in schools and economic challenges disproportionately affect girls, leading to higher dropout rates and limited career opportunities. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) emphasizes equal access to education and the elimination of gender-based discrimination, advocating for comprehensive policy reforms, curriculum changes, and awareness campaigns to foster gender sensitivity among educators and policymakers.

Reports from the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (UNESCAP) underscore the importance of integrating gender perspectives into statistical systems. This integration is vital for understanding gender disparities in educational outcomes and guiding policy decisions. Creating gender-sensitive indicators and improving data collection methodologies are essential for addressing educational inequalities and promoting gender equity. The "Global Gender Gap Report 2023" highlights notable progress in increasing access to education for women and girls but also points out ongoing challenges, especially in higher education and specialized fields. While more women are enrolling in educational programs, significant gender imbalances persist, particularly in high-paying and high-status fields, underscoring the need for targeted policies to ensure equal opportunities for all genders.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education Region 2 has implemented initiatives under the Magna Carta for Women (MCW) to promote gender equality in education. These initiatives include Learning Hubs and the Center for Development Innovation and Research (CODI), focusing on research and the dissemination of gender-sensitive teaching strategies. The Philippine Commission on Women's Gender Equality and Women Empowerment (GEWE) Plan provides a strategic framework for integrating gender perspectives into educational governance, emphasizing the need for gender-sensitive policies and programs. Globally, frameworks like the National Gender and Resource Program (NGRP) emphasize the importance of gender-responsive policies and resource allocation. UNESCO and other organizations highlight the transformative power of education in achieving gender equality while emphasizing the need for effective implementation and gender-responsive education systems. Key factors for successful gender mainstreaming include a strong governance framework, commitment from educational stakeholders, participation, resource allocation, and gender competence.

Barriers to effective gender mainstreaming include lack of awareness and understanding among staff, insufficient training, resource constraints, and socio-cultural factors. Overcoming these challenges requires comprehensive training, resource mobilization, and a commitment to challenging gender stereotypes and promoting inclusivity. In conclusion, achieving gender equality in education requires a multi-faceted approach, involving policy reforms, educational practices, and broader societal changes. The integration of gender perspectives into educational systems is crucial for creating

equitable opportunities for all genders, and continuous efforts are needed to address the persistent challenges and barriers in this area.

Critical entry points for effective gender mainstreaming efforts, identified by PCW (n.d.), include policies, flagship programs, relevant stakeholders, and enabling mechanisms. Palmén and Schmidt (2019) emphasize factors such as robust governance frameworks, commitment from all levels of the educational institution, stakeholder participation, resource allocation, and gender competence among educational stakeholders. Conversely, barriers identified by Wambeti (2016) and Kirima (2019) include staff awareness and knowledge, insufficient training, resource constraints, socio-cultural factors, and the lack of monitoring and evaluation systems.

Case studies provide insights into gender mainstreaming implementation. Nurhaeni and Kurniawan (2018) evaluated gender mainstreaming in vocational high schools, highlighting gaps between awareness and implementation. Verdonk et al. (2018) examined challenges in implementing gender mainstreaming in medical education, emphasizing the importance of political support and faculty acceptance.

Local studies echo similar themes, emphasizing the importance of integrating gender perspectives into educational practices. Domogen et al. (2022) and Duma (2022) highlight the need for intensified efforts in mainstreaming gender perspectives throughout the educational process, particularly in policy formulation and resource allocation. Hernandez and Cudiamat (2017) and Gaitan (2018) underscore the potential of gender-sensitive teaching strategies to positively impact the learning environment, emphasizing the importance of teacher training. Reyes (2018) showcases the role of higher education institutions in promoting gender equality through policy implementation and programmatic interventions.

This study investigates the implementation of gender mainstreaming within the Department of Education (DepEd) District of San Mateo, Isabela, Philippines. Initiated by the 2017 DepEd Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy, this policy underscores the importance of gender inclusivity in educational settings, aiming to address and eliminate gender biases that hinder equitable access to education. The research specifically focuses on assessing the current levels of gender mainstreaming across four critical dimensions: Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and Programs (PAPs). The objective is to identify weaknesses and gaps in these dimensions, ultimately proposing actionable recommendations to enhance the gender mainstreaming landscape in the district. This assessment employs the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF) as a guiding tool, facilitating a structured approach to evaluate existing practices and outcomes related to gender inclusivity in education.

Research Questions

1. What is the current level of Gender Mainstreaming in DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela across the following dimensions?
 - 1.1. Policy;
 - 1.2. People;

- 1.3. Enabling mechanisms; and
- 1.4. Programs, Activities, and Projects (PAPs).
2. What entry points are identified as weak and in need of significant improvement?
3. How does the overall landscape of gender mainstreaming in DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela appear based on the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF)?
4. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance Gender Mainstreaming efforts in DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the public secondary schools located within the Department of Education (DepEd) District of San Mateo, Isabela. San Mateo, a municipality in the province of Isabela, Philippines, is home to several public secondary schools that cater to students from various barangays and communities in the area. The schools involved in the study are as follows:

1. San Mateo Vocational and Industrial High School – A secondary school that offers both vocational and industrial courses alongside the regular academic curriculum. It serves as a hub for students interested in technical-vocational education and training.
2. San Mateo General Comprehensive High School – This institution provides a comprehensive high school education, offering a wide array of academic subjects and extracurricular activities for holistic student development.
3. Salinungan National High School – A secondary school located at Barangay Salinungan, San Mateo Isabela, offering junior high school programs. It aims to provide quality education to students within the nearby barangays.
4. Salinungan Stand Alone Senior High School – This school focuses solely on senior high school education, offering specialized tracks in Academics to prepare students for higher education and employment.
5. San Mateo National High School – A general secondary school that provides students with academic opportunities and extracurricular activities to foster both intellectual and personal growth.
6. Victoria Integrated School – An integrated school offering both elementary and secondary education. It caters to the needs of students from basic education up to senior high school, helping them develop their academic and technical skills.

These schools represent a diverse range of educational opportunities within the district and serve a large population of students from different backgrounds. This locale was chosen due to its accessibility, diverse student population, and variety of academic and technical programs offered in its secondary schools.

Respondents of the Study

The study adopted a universal sampling approach to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of gender mainstreaming initiatives within the San Mateo District schools. This approach allowed for the inclusion of all relevant stakeholders in the schools, which was essential to capturing a wide range of perspectives and experiences related to gender mainstreaming practices. Following the memorandum issued by Regional Gender and Development Committee (RGADC) Region 2, public schools with DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela selected participants from diverse roles—including school principals, teachers, members of the Parents-Teachers Association (PTA), and representatives from the Supreme Student Government (SSG)—the study sought to achieve an inclusive assessment of how gender initiatives are perceived and implemented across different school environments. Each group brought a unique viewpoint that enriched the evaluation process, highlighting the varied ways in which gender mainstreaming is understood, valued, and supported within the school community.

School principals, with their leadership roles, provided insights into how gender mainstreaming aligns with institutional policies and school-wide objectives, offering a managerial perspective on implementation challenges and successes. Teachers contributed firsthand observations from classroom experiences, where gender-sensitive practices directly affect student engagement and interaction. PTA members, as representatives of the local community, gave valuable input on the community's role in supporting gender mainstreaming, emphasizing the impact of parental involvement in reinforcing these values at home and in the wider community. SSG representatives added the vital student perspective, offering insights on how gender initiatives influence student life, inclusivity, and peer dynamics.

Data Gathering Instrument

The study utilized the standard Gender and Development Audit, based on the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF) toolkit developed by the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW), and a structured interview guide. The GMEF toolkit served as the primary tool for assessing the extent of gender mainstreaming within the DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela, as mandated by the Schools Division Office (SDO) Isabela. The GMEF-based questionnaire was tailored to measure organizational compliance with various Gender and Development (GAD) requirements across several dimensions, providing a standardized method to gauge progress and adherence to gender equity initiatives within educational institutions.

The questionnaire was structured into four main sections—Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and Programs/Activities/Projects (PAPs)—each targeting a specific aspect of gender mainstreaming practices. Within the Policy section, 13 descriptors assessed the institution's commitment to GAD integration, such as inclusion in strategic plans and policy issuances. The People section featured 27 items designed to measure the extent to which stakeholders, including top management, the GAD Focal Point System (GFPS), and general employees, were gender-responsive and supportive

of the organization’s GAD efforts. Participants were prompted to indicate their compliance level by selecting one of three options: "YES" for full compliance, "PARTLY YES" for partial compliance, and "NO" for non-compliance. To ensure reliability and accountability, participants were also required to provide means of verification (MOVs) or add relevant remarks to explain their responses in the MOV/Remarks column.

Furthermore, in analyzing the responses from the questionnaire, the study involved calculating the total score per entry point by adding the sub-total scores from each questionnaire section. Each entry point score was then interpreted according to a specified scale, providing a detailed measure of GAD mainstreaming across Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and PAPs. The following ranges were used to categorize the levels of compliance and development in gender mainstreaming:

RANGES	LEVEL DESCRIPTION
0.00 - 7.99 points	Level 1: Foundation Formation
8.00 - 14.99 points	Level 2: Installation of Strategic Mechanisms
15.00 - 19.99 points	Level 3: GAD Application
20.00 - 23.99 points	Level 4: Commitment Enhancement and Institutionalization
24.00 – 25.00 points	Level 5: Replication and Innovation

And to determine the overall landscape of GAD mainstreaming efforts for SDO Isabela, the scores for each entry point were summed. The total score was then assessed using an overall scale, which provided an aggregate view of the district’s gender mainstreaming level.

RANGES	LEVEL DESCRIPTION
0.00 - 30.99 points	Over-all Level 1: Foundation Formation
31.00 - 60.99 points	Over-all Level 2: Installation of Strategic Mechanisms
61.00 - 80.99 points	Over-all Level 3: GAD Application
81.00 - 95.99 points	Over-all Level 4: Commitment Enhancement and Institutionalization
96.00 – 100.00 points	Over-all Level 5: Replication and Innovation

Complementing the questionnaire, the study also utilized an interview guide to capture qualitative data, enabling a clearer understanding of gender mainstreaming implementation across schools. The interview guide was designed to gather in-depth responses from schools’ key stakeholders. It focused on uncovering experiences, challenges, and best practices in implementing GAD-related initiatives, facilitating a more comprehensive assessment beyond the quantitative data collected. These interviews provided a platform for stakeholders to elaborate on specific areas, share anecdotal insights, and discuss contextual factors that may influence the effectiveness of gender mainstreaming efforts in their respective institutions.

Data-Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering process for this study involved several structured steps to ensure a thorough and accurate collection of both quantitative and qualitative data related to Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming initiatives within the public secondary schools of San Mateo, Isabela.

The process began with the issuance of a memorandum on June 25, 2024, by Virginia G. Bilgera, chairperson of the Regional Gender and Development Committee. The memorandum was directed towards the educational sectors—including TESDA, CHED, and the Department of Education (DepEd)—mandating a comprehensive GAD audit. Following the memorandum's release, Daisy Dez Doral, the GAD focal person for DepEd Region 2, disseminated it to the Schools Division Office (SDO) of Isabela. This memorandum instructed all schools within the division to prepare for the audit by documenting their GAD compliance activities and compiling necessary reports. SDO Isabela subsequently forwarded this directive to the public secondary schools under its management, ensuring that all institutions within its jurisdiction were informed and had the necessary framework for compliance.

As part of the preparation for the GAD audit, SDO Isabela mandated each public secondary school to identify and compile Means of Verification (MOVs), which included various forms of evidence demonstrating their level of GAD implementation. Each school was required to submit an accomplishment report detailing their GAD-related activities and their alignment with regional GAD policies. These reports were intended to quantify each school's achievements and highlight their progress in gender mainstreaming. Once compiled, SDO Isabela submitted these individual school reports to the Regional GAD Focal Person, who was responsible for consolidating the data for a district-wide perspective on GAD implementation.

The formal GAD audit took place on July 24–25, 2024, at the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) in Tuguegarao City, Cagayan, under the guidance of Dr. Jhamie Tetz I. Mateo, the GAD Director for Isabela State University. During the audit, Daisy Dez Doral, acting as the GAD focal person for the DepEd sector in Region 2, presented the accomplished Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF) tool for all Schools Division Offices (SDOs) within the region. This presentation allowed for a consolidated review of the GAD initiatives across various educational institutions, offering insights into regional compliance levels, challenges, and areas for potential improvement. Following the regional GAD audit, the researcher formally requested access to the evaluation reports from SDO Isabela, with a particular focus on the San Mateo District. After the request was approved, the researcher thoroughly reviewed the GMEF evaluation copies from the six targeted schools within the district. This review allowed for a detailed examination of each school's GAD compliance levels across dimensions such as Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and Programs/Activities/Projects (PAPs).

To further enhance the depth of the data collected, the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with two representatives from each of the six schools, totaling twelve

participants. This number met the standard for data saturation, as per Creswell's (2017) recommendation, ensuring that the qualitative insights gathered were comprehensive and representative of the schools involved. These interviews focused on collecting in-depth information about the participants' challenges, experiences, and best practices regarding gender mainstreaming within their respective institutions. Interview questions were designed to capture the unique perspectives of each participant, allowing them to provide detailed responses about their school's GAD-related initiatives, perceived gaps, and areas of improvement. The interviews served to complement the quantitative data collected through the GMEF tool, providing a holistic understanding of gender mainstreaming efforts in San Mateo District's educational institutions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To address the research questions effectively, the study employed a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical tools, as well as qualitative analysis, to provide a holistic assessment of Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming within the DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela.

Descriptive Scoring System. This system was used to quantify responses according to predefined categories of gender mainstreaming maturity based on the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF). Each dimension—Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and Programs/Activities/Projects (PAPs)—was scored individually to determine its current level of GAD integration. This approach enabled a detailed description of each dimension's maturity stage, reflecting the specific effectiveness and integration of GAD within each aspect.

Sum of Scores and Aggregation. The scores from each entry point were aggregated to provide an overall GAD mainstreaming score for each school and across the district. The total scores were categorized according to GMEF-defined ranges to determine the general level of GAD mainstreaming within the district. This cumulative scoring provided a clear picture of overall GAD effectiveness and highlighted areas with potential for improvement.

Qualitative Thematic Analysis. For qualitative data gathered from interviews, thematic analysis was employed. Responses were categorized according to emerging themes in experiences, challenges, and best practices in GAD implementation. This analysis also identified entry points needing improvement and provided clear insights into stakeholder perspectives, enhancing the quantitative findings with rich, contextual data.

RESULTS

The results of the study unveiled significant insights into the levels of compliance with GAD principles across the four dimensions of gender mainstreaming:

1. **Policy:** The analysis revealed notable gaps in policy issuance, with many schools scoring low in terms of having comprehensive GAD models. Although basic

frameworks were established, a lack of depth and detail in policy implementation was evident.

2. **People:** Moderate levels of participation in GAD training were observed among staff; however, there was a limited presence of GAD champions and experts within the schools. This suggests a need for more consistent and structured training programs to build capacity and expertise among stakeholders.
3. **Enabling Mechanisms:** The study identified that while foundational GAD mechanisms were present, advanced mechanisms necessary for robust implementation were largely lacking. This indicates a need for further development and enhancement of the existing structures.
4. **Programs and Activities:** There was limited practical integration of GAD principles into both curricula and extracurricular activities. This reflects a gap in translating gender-responsive policies into tangible educational practices.

The evaluation utilizing the GMEF scoring system indicated that most schools fell within Level II or III, denoting stages of "Installation of Strategic Mechanisms" and "GAD Application," respectively. This scoring reflects varying degrees of implementation effectiveness across the district.

DISCUSSION

GMEF Entry Points	Interview Results	GMEF Results
Policy	<p>The presence of a GAD focal point observed, but a need for clearer roles and responsibilities was expressed.</p> <p>Some staff showed resistance to gender mainstreaming initiatives, perceiving them as extra work rather than essential.</p>	<p>The organization has partially adopted a GAD Agenda/Strategic Framework.</p> <p>No model GAD policies in place.</p>
People	<p>Ongoing training is needed as initial training lacked follow-up.</p> <p>Difficulty in engaging parents and the community due to traditional views.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of progress but a desire for a more structured approach.</p>	<p>Top management partly directs GAD Plan and Budget implementation.</p> <p>No staff trained on gender analysis tools.</p> <p>Partial training on sex-disaggregated data and gender statistics.</p> <p>Male employees partly involved and appreciative of GAD</p>

		<p>efforts.</p> <p>Clients partially aware of GAD efforts but unable to participate fully.</p> <p>Women do not assume critical roles.</p> <p>No recognition of staff as GAD experts.</p>
Enabling Mechanisms	<p>Efforts to incorporate gender into lesson plans, though implementation varies.</p> <p>Lack of gender-sensitive teaching materials noted as a barrier.</p>	<p>No sex-disaggregated database or enhanced M&E system.</p> <p>Partial utilization of budget for GAD PAPs.</p> <p>No centralized database accessible to regional offices.</p> <p>GAD Focal Point and other mechanisms not recognized as models.</p> <p>No Knowledge Management System for GAD-related knowledge products.</p>
(Programs, Activities, and Projects) PAPs	<p>Challenges in engaging parents/community, and resistance from staff to gender mainstreaming.</p> <p>Acknowledgment of progress but need for more structured approach.</p>	<p>Partial basic GAD orientation conducted.</p> <p>Partial consultation with clients to identify gender issues.</p> <p>No GAD section on the website.</p> <p>No use of gender analysis tools in the development planning cycle.</p> <p>Partial monitoring of GAD PAPs implementation.</p> <p>No deepening sessions based on updated GAD policies.</p>

		No impact evaluation of GAD PAPs.
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The table provided summarizes the results from an evaluation of Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming efforts in an organization based on the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF). Below is a comprehensive discussion of the findings organized by four main entry points: Policy, People, Enabling Mechanisms, and Programs, Activities, and Projects (PAPs).

1. Policy

The evaluation highlights the organization's limited progress in embedding GAD principles at the policy level. While a GAD focal point exists, its role lacks clarity in terms of specific duties and responsibilities. This ambiguity may contribute to inconsistent application of gender mainstreaming initiatives across different departments. Some staff perceive GAD-related tasks as extra work rather than a critical aspect of organizational function, indicating a lack of understanding or appreciation for GAD objectives. Although there is partial adoption of a GAD Agenda or Strategic Framework, the organization has not established model policies that could serve as benchmarks for best practices in gender mainstreaming.

2. People

The findings show a mixed level of GAD engagement and awareness among staff, clients, and the broader community. Initial GAD training has been conducted, but follow-up has been insufficient, resulting in a need for ongoing training and capacity-building efforts. Engaging parents and the community present challenges due to prevailing traditional views on gender roles, which limits broader acceptance and support for GAD initiatives. Though some progress has been acknowledged, a more structured approach to GAD implementation is desired. Top management has partially taken on the responsibility of directing GAD plan and budget execution; however, a significant gap remains in specialized training on gender analysis tools. While there is some training on sex-disaggregated data and gender statistics, it is limited, reducing the organization's ability to make data-driven decisions on gender issues. Male employees have shown some involvement and appreciation for GAD efforts, yet women's participation in critical decision-making roles is lacking, as is the formal recognition of GAD expertise among staff members.

3. Enabling Mechanisms

The organization has made efforts to incorporate gender perspectives into lesson plans, but the degree of implementation varies significantly, potentially affecting consistency in GAD education and awareness efforts. A significant barrier is the lack of gender-sensitive teaching materials, which restricts the organization's ability to convey equitable and inclusive messaging. Additionally, there is no sex-disaggregated database

or enhanced Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) system to track GAD progress, and budget allocation for GAD programs, activities, and projects (PAPs) is only partially utilized. The absence of a centralized, accessible database for regional offices further hinders collaboration and information sharing. Although the organization has a GAD focal point, it lacks recognition as a model mechanism, which may limit its influence and efficacy. Furthermore, there is no established Knowledge Management System to consolidate and disseminate GAD-related knowledge products, a gap that could otherwise support continuous learning and improvement in gender mainstreaming practices.

4. Programs, Activities, and Projects (PAPs)

The organization faces multiple challenges in engaging parents and the community, and some staff continue to resist gender mainstreaming. Although the organization has made some progress, there is a strong need for a more structured and coherent approach. Basic GAD orientation sessions have been held, but they are not comprehensive, and client consultations on gender issues are limited. There is no dedicated GAD section on the organization's website, which could serve as a valuable resource for raising awareness and engaging clients. The use of gender analysis tools in the development planning cycle is absent, and GAD PAPs are only partially monitored, reducing the organization's ability to assess their impact fully. Additionally, no in-depth sessions on updated GAD policies have been conducted, and there is a lack of impact evaluation on GAD PAPs, both of which are critical for refining and validating GAD initiatives.

These GMEF findings underscore the DepEd District of San Mateo, Isabela's initial steps toward GAD mainstreaming while highlighting significant gaps in policy clarity, staff training, community engagement, and structural support mechanisms. Moving forward, it is recommended that the organization clarifies GAD focal point roles, invests in continuous gender analysis training, strengthens enabling mechanisms such as data management systems, and formalizes model policies that integrate GAD as a foundational rather than supplementary element across the organization's practices. Establishing these improvements could foster a more inclusive and gender-responsive environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher strongly recommends adopting the following GAD plan to enhance and solidify gender mainstreaming efforts within the San Mateo District. This plan is designed to address identified gaps and build on existing strengths to provide a more consistent and impactful approach to gender equality across all facets of the district's educational environment.

GAD Mandate	Gender issue	Cause of Gender Issue	GAD Result Statement/GAD objective	Relevant Organization MFO/PAP or PPA	GAD Activity
Encourage Equal Participation	Unclear Roles and Responsibilities in the GAD Focal Point	The GAD focal point exists, but roles and responsibilities are not clearly defined, leading to confusion and inefficiency.	Establish clear roles and responsibilities for the GAD focal point to enhance organizational capacity and effectiveness in gender mainstreaming.	GAD Focal Point and Organizational Policies	<p>Policy: Develop and communicate a clear policy defining the roles and responsibilities of the GAD focal point.</p> <p>People: Train GAD focal point staff on their specific roles in gender mainstreaming.</p> <p>Enabling Mechanisms: Integrate clear GAD focal point roles into the organizational structure and workflow.</p> <p>PAPs: Hold a workshop for the GAD focal point team to align their efforts and responsibilities with the strategic GAD framework.</p>
Promote Gender-	Resistance to Gender	Some staff perceive gender	Cultivate an organizational	GAD Strategy Implementati	<p>Policy: Revise the</p>

Fair Language	Mainstreaming Among Staff	mainstreaming as additional work, leading to resistance in implementing GAD initiatives.	culture that understands and embraces gender mainstreaming as an essential function.	on and Organizational Culture	<p>GAD policy to emphasize the integration of gender mainstreaming in all aspects of work.</p> <p>People: Conduct awareness and sensitization sessions for staff on the importance and benefits of gender mainstreaming.</p> <p>Enabling Mechanisms: Develop a reward and recognition system to acknowledge staff involvement in gender mainstreaming.</p> <p>PAPs: Organize an awareness campaign to highlight successful GAD initiatives and their positive impact on the organization.</p>
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<p>Teach Empathy and Respect</p>	<p>Inadequate Gender Sensitivity Training for Staff</p>	<p>Initial training lacks follow-up, leading to gaps in staff knowledge and skills related to gender analysis and data.</p>	<p>Ensure ongoing and comprehensive training for staff on gender mainstreaming, with a focus on tools for gender analysis and data.</p>	<p>GAD Training and Development Programs</p>	<p>Policy: Include mandatory follow-up gender training as part of the staff development policy. People: Implement a structured, ongoing training program for staff, focusing on gender analysis tools and the use of sex-disaggregated data. Enabling Mechanisms: Create an internal knowledge-sharing platform for continuous learning on gender issues. PAPs: Conduct quarterly gender workshops with follow-up assessments to ensure the application of gender analysis in</p>
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					daily operations.
Encourage Equal Participation	Limited Engagement of Parents and Community in GAD Activities	Traditional views on gender and resistance from the community hinder full engagement and participation.	Enhance the involvement of parents and the community in GAD activities, using culturally sensitive approaches.	GAD Community Outreach Programs	<p>Policy: Revise community engagement policies to include gender-sensitive language and practices.</p> <p>People: Organize community sensitization programs that address traditional gender roles and encourage active participation.</p> <p>Enabling Mechanisms: Create a gender-sensitive outreach team to work with parents and community leaders.</p> <p>PAPs: Host gender workshops and family involvement sessions to raise awareness and foster community-</p>

					based gender initiatives.
Inclusive Curriculum Design	Lack of Gender-Sensitive Teaching Materials	Gender-sensitive teaching materials are not available or utilized, limiting the integration of gender perspectives in education.	Ensure the availability and use of gender-sensitive teaching materials in all educational programs.	Gender Integration in Education Programs	<p>Policy: Adopt a policy that mandates the inclusion of gender-sensitive materials in the curriculum.</p> <p>People: Train educators on the creation and use of gender-sensitive teaching materials.</p> <p>Enabling Mechanisms: Develop and distribute a repository of gender-sensitive teaching materials accessible to all educators.</p> <p>PAPs: Organize workshops for educators on the integration of gender perspectives into lesson plans and classroom activities.</p>
Use Diverse Grouping	Incomplete Gender Data and	No centralized sex-disaggregated	Develop a comprehensive M&E system	GAD Monitoring and	<p>Policy: Create a policy for the</p>

	Monitoring Systems	database or monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system to track GAD activities and impacts.	that integrates sex-disaggregated data and tracks the impact of GAD programs.	Evaluation Framework	collection and utilization of sex-disaggregated data in all GAD programs. People: Train staff on the use of gender analysis tools and the importance of sex-disaggregated data. Enabling Mechanisms: Set up a centralized data collection and analysis system for GAD-related activities. PAPs: Implement an M&E system that tracks GAD outcomes, with regular reporting and assessments on gender-related programs and initiatives.
Challenge Gender Stereotypes	Limited Use of Gender Analysis Tools in Planning	Gender analysis tools are not consistently used in the development planning cycle,	Integrate gender analysis tools into the development planning cycle to ensure	GAD Planning and Strategy	Policy: Establish a policy requiring the use of gender analysis tools

		affecting the integration of gender considerations.	gender-sensitive planning and decision-making.		in all project and program planning. People: Provide training on gender analysis tools and their application in the development planning process. Enabling Mechanisms: Integrate gender analysis tools into planning templates and guidelines. PAPs: Conduct gender-sensitive planning sessions, where participants use gender analysis tools to inform decision-making and project design.
Reflect on Teacher Biases	Lack of Impact Evaluation for GAD Activities	GAD activities are not regularly evaluated for their effectiveness, leading to limited improvement	Implement regular impact evaluations for GAD programs and activities to assess effectiveness and guide improvements.	GAD Impact Assessment and Monitoring	Policy: Implement a policy that requires impact evaluations of GAD activities at regular

		and accountability.			<p>intervals.</p> <p>People: Build the capacity of staff to design and conduct impact evaluations using gender analysis frameworks.</p> <p>Enabling Mechanisms: Establish an evaluation framework that incorporates both qualitative and quantitative data on gender-related outcomes.</p> <p>PAPs: Conduct annual evaluations of GAD programs and use the results to adjust and improve future initiatives.</p>
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed procedural ethical guidelines to protect the rights and well-being of all the participating teachers. Prior to their involvement, all teachers will receive a comprehensive explanation of the study's purpose, objectives, and voluntary nature through the so-called informed consent. Their participation is entirely optional, with the assurance that withdrawal is possible at any stage without repercussions.

All collected data, including personal information, will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be stored securely. The study prioritizes privacy, avoiding inquiries into personal matters unrelated to research objectives. Participants will be informed about potential benefits and the avoidance of harm during the study. The right to withdraw without providing a reason will be respected throughout the entire research process. Transparent communication about research procedures, peer review, and institutional approval ensures clarity. Teacher participants will be offered the option to receive feedback on the study's findings, and research dissemination will be conducted responsibly. Cultural sensitivity will be maintained, and continuous evaluation will address emerging ethical concerns, ensuring adherence to ethical research conduct.

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